

In step (5), IO_3^- completes the oxidation of the chlorine species to chlorate, which has been found to have no inhibiting action at comparable concentration. Summing these reactions, we get

where (6) = (1) + (2) + (3) + (4) + (5) ... (6)

The reaction is the oxidation of chloride to chlorate by iodate and Mn(III) ions.

Finally, adding to (6), the oxidation of Mn(II) by IO_3^- [equation (a)] and the disproportionation of HIO_2 i.e.,

We get the overall reaction

where (7) = 2(6) + 2(a) + (b)

The mechanism proposed, however, need not be the only one which may account for the effect of chloride ions.

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Quantitative Oxidation of Some Hydrazine Derivatives with Ammonium Hexanitratocerate(IV) as the Oxidant

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HYDRAZINE and its derivatives are quantitatively oxidised with certain organic and inorganic reagents. Barakat and Shaker¹ developed a method for the determination of hydrazines with N-bromosuccinimide in dilute sulphuric acid medium. Iodine monochloride², Fehling's solution³⁻⁵ and ceric sulphate⁶ are the chief inorganic oxidants used for the determination of hydrazine derivatives. Bromate-bromide mixture⁷ in acidic medium has also been employed for the oxidative determination of some hydrazines. Berka and Busev⁸ described an indirect potentiometric method for hydrazine sulphate using Thallium (III) as an oxidant. In the present paper a simple method has been described for the determination of hydrazine

derivatives at the mg level using ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) as the oxidising agent.

Experimental

Hydrazine samples were dissolved in distilled water in a 100 ml volumetric flask to give a concentration of ≈ 1 mg/ml. Ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) solution (0.15N) A.R., B.D.H. : 8 g was dissolved in 0.5M nitric acid in a 100 ml volumetric flask. Ferrous ammonium sulphate solution (Fe II) (0.025N) A.R., B.D.H. : 2.4508 g was dissolved in distilled water in 250 ml volumetric flask. 5 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid was added and the solution made up to the mark with distilled water. Sulphuric acid (1M) : 1M solution of sulphuric acid (v/v) was prepared by dissolving A.R., B.D.H. sample in distilled water. Indicator, 0.001M : Ferroin solution (v/v) in distilled water.

Procedure : An aliquot containing 1-5 mg of the sample was taken in a 100 ml conical flask and 5 ml of 0.15N ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) was added. The flask was stoppered and shaken well. The contents were allowed to react for 10 min at room temperature (25°). After the reaction was over, the stopper was rinsed with 5 ml of distilled water and 10 ml of 1M sulphuric acid was added and the contents shaken for a minute. The unreacted ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) was titrated against ferrous ammonium sulphate using ferroin indicator. A blank was also run under identical conditions. The recovery of the sample was calculated with the difference in the titre value of the ferrous ammonium sulphate for the sample and the blank.

Results and Discussion

Before applying the method for hydrazine group of compounds, the reaction conditions were developed with hydrazine sulphate. Effect of Ce(IV) concentration, reaction time, reaction temperature and concentration of nitric acid were studied. It was found that 0.15N concentration of Ce(IV) reagent is sufficient for quantitative results. The oxidation of all the compounds could be completed within 10 minutes except semicarbazide and 2-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone which require 20 minutes. The method is applicable even for the higher sample size without loss of accuracy and reproducibility.

The presence of sulphuric acid helps in detecting sharp and distinct end points. The stoichiometry of the reaction was established for every compound by reacting 1-5 mg of the sample for different intervals of reaction time at room temperature with a calculated excess of Ce(IV) reagent. The reaction was carried out at 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 min and the recovery of the sample was calculated. It was found that the consumption of Ce(IV) goes on increasing with increase in reaction time and attain a constant value at 20 minutes. In this way it was found that the consumption of Ce(IV) for phenylhydrazine hydrochloride, semicarbazide, hydrazine

sulphate, hydrazine dihydrochloride, N-N-diphenyl hydrazine and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone was 5, 7, 4, 6 and 6 mol respectively.

The recommended procedure was applied for the determination of phenyl hydrazine hydrochloride, semicarbazide, hydrazine sulphate, hydrazine dihydrochloride, N-N'-diphenyl hydrazine and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone derivatives. Amounts ranging from 1, 2 and 3 mg were taken and three experiments were performed for each sample size. The average % error reported for phenylhydrazine hydrochloride was ± 0.45 , semicarbazide ± 0.33 , hydrazine sulphate ± 0.54 , hydrazine dihydrochloride ± 0.69 , N-N-diphenyl hydrazine ± 0.59 , and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone ± 0.79 . On the whole the deviation of the results is within 1%.

Considering the oxidation reaction of hydrazine derivatives and the number of equivalents of Ce(IV) consumed for a particular sample, the following course of reactions (Fig. 1) may be suggested for the oxidation of hydrazine derivatives.

Fig. 1. Proposed course of reaction for the oxidation of hydrazine derivatives.

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Effect of Electrolytes on the Creaming and Demulsification of O/W Emulsions Stabilized by Soaps

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A survey of literature reveals that oil/water emulsions have been prepared by employing soaps¹, protein+soaps², saponin+soaps³, resin soaps⁴ and metal soaps⁵ as emulsifiers. Their properties such as surface tension⁶, viscosity³, creaming⁷, aging⁷ etc have been studied. But the authors have introduced 2-pyridine ethanol sod. oleate as new soap and have studied its physical properties⁸. After studying the physical properties of oil/water emulsions⁹ stabilized by 2-pyridine ethanol sod. oleate, it was thought worthwhile to present a systematic data of creaming and demulsification concentration of different electrolytes for these emulsions.

Experimental

Double distilled kerosene (sp. gr. 0.7948 g/ml), turpentine (sp. gr. 0.8745 g/ml) and water having conductance $1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ were used in all the experiments. All the electrolytes used were of BDH, AR grade. 2-Pyridine ethanol sodium oleate has been prepared by refluxing 2-pyridine ethanol, oleic acid and NaOH in equimolar ratio⁹.

Preparation of emulsions : O/W emulsions have been prepared by taking kerosene, turpentine and mixed oil (50% kerosene+50% turpentine) as internal phase and water as external phase in the ratio of 1 : 3 and soap concentration was kept 1% constant by agent-in-water method⁹.

Five test-tubes were taken and labeled 1,2,3,4,5 and 5 ml of N/10 solution of the electrolytes investigated were added to tubes 1,2,3,4 and 5 respectively and the total volume made to 5 ml by adding suitable volumes of conductivity water. To each of the mixture 5 ml of emulsions was added and kept undisturbed for 6 hrs. Two concentrations of electrolytes have been experimentally determined ; (i) the concentration at which the emulsion is separated into a dilute emulsion layer and thick or viscous creamed layer and (ii) the concentration at which the emulsion is separated into a aqueous